

Impact of Library Resources on Academic Performance of Senior Students in Government Owned Secondary Schools in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Utilization of learning resources is imperative in the administration of learning institutions as it enhances better achievement of school goals. Evidence of poor academic performance in public secondary schools has given credence to this study. It is aimed at investigating the impact of library resources on academic performance of senior students in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada metropolis, Ahoada East local government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. These schools include Federal Science and Technical College, Western Country Boys High School, Government Girls Secondary School and Government Technical College. Survey design was adopted for the study. Research instrument was a questionnaire. Population for the study was 3,163 and Taro Yamen formula to determine sample size of 355. Questionnaire was distributed directly and collected by the researcher within the respective schools with the assistance of a head teacher in each of the schools. Data collected was analyzed using simple percentages and mean. The result of the findings indicated the need for adequate provision of textbooks, electronic books and audio-visual resources to improve students' academic performance. To this end, it was recommended that Federal and State Governments establish well stocked school libraries with professional librarians; education providers and policy makers integrate ICT with education and train teachers and students on same. Finally, there should be provision of specialized educational gadgets to modernize education and support learning pattern of students. There should also be supervision and monitoring in the use of audio-visual resources.

Keywords: Impact, Library Resources, Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

School libraries refer to libraries domiciled in pre-primary, primary and secondary schools. Their main purpose is to provide library resources to support the teaching and learning process. It is in line with the importance of libraries to the educational process that the National Policy on Education (2004) states that in pursuance of the goals of primary education in Nigeria, government shall provide the following education services.

- i. School Library
- ii. Education Resource Centres
- iii. Specialist Teachers and Librarians

However, inspite of this policy most of these schools have no libraries, while those that have lack information resources, appropriate infrastructure and space to mention a few. Moreover the deplorable state of school library development in Nigeria to a great extent affects learning outcomes (academic performance) and impedes the ability of students to think creatively and have independent study needed for education.

Statement of the Problem

The role of library information resources (print and non-print), in the enhancement of student academic performance cannot be overemphasize. The purpose of the school libraries is to support teaching and learning. This cannot be achieved without a proper learning environment which includes adequate supply of sufficient and relevant information resources to support same. To this end, attention has been drawn to the availability of information resources accessible to students. Regrettably, this has been an issue in schools in recent times. Some of the effects over time include poor performance at both in internal and external exams e.g. WAEC, NECO and NABTEB for the senior students who often result to malpractice. The researcher is at a loss why it is not a priority given the circumstances. This is the gap the study intended to fill. It was carried out to investigate the impact of library resources on the academic performance of senior students in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada metropolis, Ahoada Local Government Area, Rivers State,

Nigeria. It seeks to solve these problems and help to promote students' learning outcome through the provision of available and accessible information resources.

Objectives of the Study

The research is based on the following objectives:

1. To determine the impact of library textbooks on academic performance in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State.
2. To ascertain the impact of library electronic books on academic performance in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State.
3. To establish the impact of library audio-video resources on academic performance in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government

Research Questions

The research is set out to provide answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the impact of library textbooks on academic performance in government owned secondary school students in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State?
2. What is the impact of library electronic textbooks on academic performance in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada East local government area, Rivers State.
- What is the impact of library audio-visual resources on academic performance in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada East local government area, Rivers State.

Literature Review/Theoretical Framework

Library resources also referred to as information resources, are sources through which information can be gotten in order to satisfy the needs of users. Batigi (2014) stated that information resources constitute variety of materials in which information could be stored, retrieved and disseminated for use. Adamu *et al.*,(2023) corroborated same that information resources are those resources that are in print, non-print and electronic formats such as textbooks, journals, indexes, abstracts, newspapers, magazines, reports, compact disc, audio-visuals,

microfilms, microfiche, websites, online databases, electronic journals electronic books etc.

Arua and Chinaka (2011) opined that school library information resources are seen as all inputs which are utilized in the library in order to provide good learning environment for students and teachers so as to be able to achieve educational goals i.e. high academic performance. Library resources are therefore essential to facilitate the school library's functions among which are:

- i. To thoroughly provide information resources necessary for the school's educational programmes
- ii. To help in improving and raising reading skills and habits of students.

The school library information resources are seen as inputs which are utilized to in order to provide and promote good learning environment for students and teachers to achieve educational goals.

Theoretical framework of the study is based on the theory of academic performance (TOP) developed by Elger (2007). It emphasizes six foundational concepts to form a framework that can be used to explain performance as well as performance improvements. They are, context, level of knowledge, levels of skill, levels of identify, personal factors and fixed factors. Three axioms are proposed for effective performance improvements. These include mindset, immersion in an enriching environment and engagement in reflective practice. Also, Walberg's theory of educational productivity posits that psychological characteristics of individuals' students and their immediate psychological environments influence educational outcomes (cognitive, behavioural and attitudinal, Reyold &Walberg, 1992). These two theories have implications for this study because they emphasize the need for enriching and enabling environment (learning environment) as an important factor for effective academic performance. The learning environment in this context includes external factors like the library, availability library resources (print and none-print), the home, parental support etc, which play supportive role in conjunction with the school. With respect to this study therefore, immersion in an enriching "environment" refers to the learning environment or immediate psychological environment as postulated by Walberg.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey design to investigate the impact of library resources on academic performance of senior students in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East local government area, Rivers State. The four public secondary schools used for the study were: Federal Science and Technical College, County Boys High School, Government Girls Secondary School and Government Technical College, all in Ahoada-East Local Government Area of Rivers State. The population of this study comprised of 3163 students from the

aforementioned schools, while Taro Yamen Formula was used to determine the sample size of 355 for this study. The instrument for eliciting data was a structured questionnaire. Data was analyzed using simple percentage and mean.

Data analysis and discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: What is the impact of textbooks on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East, Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 1: Impact of textbooks on Academic performance of students in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local government Area, Rivers State.

S/N	ITEMS	N = 355	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Σ %	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Promote ability to gain knowledge from experts in different subject		274	77.1	76	21.4	3	0.85	2	0.5	100	3.75	Agree
2	It enhances reading culture		200	56.3	142	40.0	10	2.17	3	0.8	100	3.52	Agree
3	Enhances personal study		236	66.4	112	31.6	14	3.94	3	0.8	100	3.64	Agree
4	Creates conducive learning environment		208	58.6	116	32.7	17	4.79	14	3.9	100	3.46	Agree
GRAND MEAN												3.59	

Note: Criterion Mean – 2.5

Table 1 reveals that 98.59% of students agree that the availability of textbooks promotes knowledge from experts in diverse subjects, 96.34% indicate that it enhances reading culture, 98.03% agree it enhances personal study while 91.27% infer that it creates a conducive learning environment. This shows that availability of textbooks enhances the academic performance of the students. This is agreement with Li and Wang (2024) that students’ use of chemistry textbooks improved their interests, attitudes and performance. Warsame (2023) also stated in his study that students’ progress and academic achievement are linked to the availability of textbooks. Pavesic and Cankar (2022) also corroborate that there is a link between the use of

textbooks and students learning outcome. They also state that as a result of this, there is the need to systematically collect information on the use of textbooks among students and follow the effects on achievement to improve the quality of future textbooks. It therefore shows that in availability of textbooks is one of the reason for poor academic performance within the region.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of electronic books on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Respondent on the Impact of Electronic Books on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary Students in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers state.

S/ N	ITEMS	N = 355	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Σ %	\bar{X}	Decision
5	Enhances easy accessibility to information		246	62.3	104	29.3	2	0.56	3	0.85	100	3.67	Agree
6	It has a wider coverage for subjects		190	53.5	153	43.1	8	2.54	4	0.27	100	3.49	Agree
7	Easy access to multiple books		215	60.6	129	36.3	11	3.10	-	-	100	2.85	Agree
8	Access to local and foreign literature		203	51.2	122	34.4	17	4.79	13	3.66	100	3.45	Agree
GRAND MEAN												3.37	

Table 2 reveals that 91.60% agree that electronic books enhances their accessibility to information, 96.62% state it enables a wider coverage of subjects, 96.90% indicate it allows for easy access to multiple books while 91.55% state that it enhances access to local and foreign literature. Invariably, if they were exposed to electronic books it would enable them perform better. This is in line with Chinweuba, Ugwuanyi and Eseadi (2024) that learner’s access to e-books significantly impacted how well they performed in physics. Sum and Pan

(2021) corroborate same that use o e-book in teaching enhances their creativity and learning motivation. This implies that there in availability of electronic books for the students leading to low academic performance.

Research Questions 3: What is the impact of audio-visual resources on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ahoada Metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Table 3: Impact of audio-visual resources on academic performance of senior secondary students in Ahoada metropolis, Ahoada East Local Government area, Rivers State.

S/ N	ITEMS	N = 355	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Σ %	\bar{X}	Decision
9	Easy access to resources		181	50.2	155	43.66	14	3.94	5	1.41	100	3.44	Agree
10	Encourages teach your self-method		220	61.9	118	33.24	17	4.79	-	-	100	3.57	Agree
11	Enhances feedback teaching and learning method		225	63.4	120	33.80	10	2.82	-	-	100	3.61	Agree
12	Promote on-hand evaluation		170	47.9	165	46.48	13	3.66	7	1.97	100	3.40	Agree
GRAND MEAN												3.51	

Table 3 reveals that 94.65% affirm that audio-visual resources give easy access to resources, 95.21% indicate that it encourages teach yourself method, 97.18% state that it enhances feedback method, while 94.37% indicate promotes on-hand evaluation. This shows that the integration of audio-visual resources will improve the academic performance of the students. This is in agreement

with Alabi *et al.*, (2021) that audio-visual materials had positive effect on students’ academic performance. Ajogbeje, Osuntuji & Awodu stated in their study that audio-visual materials influences students’ academic performance in physics in secondary schools in Ikweore local government area of Ekiti Stte, Nigeria. They concluded that when appropriate media (i.e audio-visuals) are

integrated into the curriculum to complement the traditional methods, higher learning outcomes in terms of achievement scores would probably result. They stressed that secondary students taught with materials achieved better than those taught with the traditional method. This also implies that there would have been improvement in the academic achievement of student's integration of audio-visual materials in the schools.

CONCLUSION

This research investigated the impact of library resources and academic performance of senior students in government owned secondary schools in Ahoada metropolis, Ahoada East local government area, Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that availability of adequate textbooks, electronic books and audio-visual resources to support teaching and learning impacted greatly on the academic performance of students. It also revealed that the scarcity of these instructional resources led to poor academic achievement. In the light of this it cannot be overemphasized that the teaching and process is directly linked to the availability of relevant learning resources because it determines the students' academic performance. Therefore, steps are to be taken to mitigate the challenges for better achievement of school goals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations should therefore be considered:

1. Federal and state governments funding for the stocked school libraries (print and non-print resources) as well as professional librarians to meet user's needs.
2. Education providers and policy makers need to consider different ways of integrating ICT with education and training teachers and students in this clime.
3. Provision of specialized educational gadgets at affordable prices to modernize educational system and support academic performance and learning attitudes of students. In addition, there should be supervision and monitoring of audio-visual teaching aids.

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